

Macro-Financial Augmentation of the Recursive Ripple Model in UK Regional Housing Markets

University of Bath - BSc Economics

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Abstract

This study augments the multidimensional ripple-effect model by integrating macro-financial fundamentals into an ARDL-ECM framework for UK regional house prices (1973 Q4 to 2015 Q2). Controlling for employment, GDP, CPI, and interest rate shocks, we find that robust spatial and vintage-specific spillovers persist. Albeit mildly attenuated, this study demonstrates local contagion beyond aggregate trends.

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1. Introduction

House prices lie at the heart of macroeconomic stability and household welfare. In the United Kingdom (UK), stark regional disparities have profound implications for wealth effects, collateral values and financial sector resilience. Although a wide literature already documents the ‘ripple effect’, whereby shocks in one region transmits to its neighbours, two notable gaps remain unstudied. Firstly, most studies treat the housing stock as homogeneous, despite the clear differences across ‘old’, ‘modern’ and ‘new’ house-types. Secondly, few existing analyses fully account for the macro-financial backdrop of an economy, such as national employment, GDP growth, inflation and interest rate fluctuations. However, these macroeconomic fundamentals can induce spurious cross-regional co-movements if left omitted.

This dissertation addresses these gaps by augmenting the multidimensional ripple model of Hudson et al. (2017). To do this, we disaggregate regional house-price indices into three vintages: old, modern and new. This allows us to capture how dwelling characteristics shape the amplitude and persistence of spatial spillovers. Simultaneously, we also embed for key macro-financial controls into an Autoregressive Distributed Lag-Error-Correction (ARDL-ECM) framework, thereby separating genuine local contagion from broad shocks.

Our analysis covers all twelve regions in Great Britain by employing quarterly price series from Nationwide, over the period of 1973 Q4 to 2015 Q2. After unit-root testing (ADF and PP), we estimate conditional ECMs with Newey-West standard errors. This approach ensures robust inference on both short-run and long-run dynamics.

In this study, we find that local house-price growth exhibits strong self-correcting forces, with deviations from the equilibrium tending to be significantly eroded over the following quarter. Moreover, spillovers between vintages are clearly differentiated; modern stock shocks reliably spur new-build activity, whereas the influence of existing older stock is more nuanced and yields mixed impacts of the housing market. Spatial contagion remains pronounced once macro-financial variables are controlled, as neighbour-average growth coefficients are shown to be

highly significant. This demonstrates that genuine inter-regional interaction persists beyond common macro-financial influences. Although the inclusion of macro-financial control does not ultimately temper the strength of ripple effects, it does eliminate them. This highlights the dual importance of aggregate economic conditions and local network dynamics.

By combining vintage disaggregation with macro-financial controls, this study refines our understanding of regional housing interdependencies. It also offers policymakers improved tools for stress testing and regional planning, and overall helps to distinguish broad economic cycles from genuine spatial contagion.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The UK Housing Market and the Ripple Effect

The dynamics of UK house prices have long attracted scholarly attention, mainly due to their importance towards household wealth, individual's financial stability and for monetary policy. Early empirical studies document persistent regional disparities and the phenomenon whereby price changes in one region influence those in adjacent areas (also known as the 'ripple effect'). Holmans (1995) and Drake (1995) first observed that shocks in London tended to propagate Northwest and Southwest across the UK and established that neighbouring regions experience stronger reactions in shorter time periods. These findings highlighted how co-movement among regional house-price series is created by spatial arbitrage, which is driven by migration, commuting patterns and investment flows.

2.2 Testing Approaches

Subsequent research then formalised b-convergence and s-convergence concepts. Respectively, these concepts demonstrate faster growth from lower priced markets and narrowing cross-sectional dispersion (Cook, 2003). However, unit-root tests and cointegration continued to produce contradictory outcomes, which was often due to the imbalance between power and magnitude and the neglect of asymmetric adjustments (Meen, 2002; Cook, 2003). Therefore, to address these limitations, Pesaran et al. (2001) developed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach that accommodates for a mix of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ regressors. Payne (2012) demonstrated the framework's efficiency in U.S. house price data and Hudson et al. (2017) became the first to apply ARDL-ECM to a UK context. Both studies demonstrated robust cointegration among house price series and their neighbouring average equivalents.

2.3 Ripple Model Literature

Early ripple literature often assumed the UK to behave as a star network emanating from the capital (London) (Alexander and Barrow, 1994; Holmes and Grimes, 2008). However, this perspective fails to consider the bi-directional feedbacks among secondary regions. Hence, Holly et al. (2011) critiqued the star model and instead argued that shocks propagate recursively through all adjacent regions, and then eventually feed back to region A. This multidimensional ripple model was captured by averaging prices over each region's bordering neighbours. Gray (2015) further confirmed that ripple speeds and amplitudes vary by geographical proximity as well as underlying economic ties. Hudson et al. (2017) later adopted this framework, using quarterly data from 1973 to 2014. This study uncovered statistically significant spillovers in every UK region when conditioning on neighbour average indices.

2.4 Vintage Disaggregation

A further complication is posed by housing heterogeneity as not all dwellings are perfect substitutes, as they differ in location, quality and buyer preferences. Considering this, Gray (2015) distinguished between 'old', 'modern' and 'new' houses and found significant differences in cyclical and seasonality. Using spectral methods, the study demonstrated that modern and old vintages co-move more closely with each other than with new builds, especially during cycle extremes. Balcilar et al. (2013) and Lean and Smyth (2013) also extended this ripple analysis to other economies, again establishing vintage-specific spillover patterns. Hudson et al. (2017) then combined vintage disaggregation with multidimensional ripple modelling and revealed that ripples stemming from shocks differ between house types, each creating strong inter-vintage feedback loops.

2.5 Macro-Financial Fundamentals

Despite existing spatial ripple literature successfully demonstrating inter-regional spillovers, a notable omission in most studies is the explicit control for macro-financial fundamentals. The failure to consider these broad forces risks conflating genuine spatial propagation with macroeconomic shocks. For example, Muellbauer

and Murphy (1997) demonstrate that fluctuations in aggregate income and interest rates can induce co-movement across regional housing markets that mimics spatial spillovers. Thus, by failing to account for these shocks, standard ARDL-ECM specification may overstate the magnitude and significance of neighbour-average coefficients.

In the UK context, although Hudson et al. (2017) robustly establishes network spillovers with vintage-stratified markets, the study leaves macro-financial fundamentals implicit. However, Bank of England (2019) stress that national employment cycles, credit growth, economic growth and inflation expectations are central to regional housing volatility. Therefore, one fails to confirm whether an observed ripple reflects a true spillover or a contemporaneous response, without incorporating macroeconomic variable controls. My dissertation addresses this gap by employing the ARDL-ECM framework with the integration of four key macro-financial variables: UK employment growth, real GDP growth, consumer-price inflation and the Bank of England's official rate. This augmentation allows for a cleaner separation of local network effects from aggregate shocks and yields a more reliable inference on the true spatial dynamics of vintage-specific house-price transmission.

3. Model Specification

3.1 Simultaneous System

In regional housing markets, prices are determined by the interaction of supply and demand. Supply reflects the willingness of property owners to sell their homes, and this depends on the prevailing prices and the relative attractiveness of alternative assets. On the other hand, demand arises from buyers. A buyer's valuation of a property depends on not solely local prices; prices of adjacent regions and broader macro-financial conditions are also considered.

To capture these interdependencies in our model we let $p(i, j, t)$ denote the algorithm of the average price of housing type i (new, modern, or old) in region j and time t . We group the three types into the vector

$$P_{j,t} = \begin{pmatrix} P_{new,j,t} \\ P_{mod,j,t} \\ P_{old,j,t} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

This vertical notation allows us to write both supply and demand for all three house types simultaneously. Also, we can recognise that supply of one type may respond to price changes in the other two types. Thus, this reflects, for instance, that owners of old houses may delay sale if modern houses become relatively expensive.

3.1.1 Incorporating Spatial Spillovers

Existing literature (Cook and Holly, 2000; Holly et al., 2011) and intuitive housing market dynamics both clearly point towards a 'ripple' effect: a price shock in one region propagates to its neighbours. To model this, we define $N(j)$ as the set of regions that share a border with j . Then, we construct the neighbour-average price vector:

$$P_{j,t}^N = \frac{1}{|N(j)|} \sum_{k \in N(j)} P_{k,t} \quad (2)$$

Taking an unweighted average imposes a parsimonious structure where each neighbour contributes equally to j 's demand.

3.1.2 Role of Macro-Financial Fundamentals

House prices are not solely dependent on local factors; they also respond to a variety of macro-financial variables. As shown in the literature, main variables include aggregate employment trends (a proxy for income and mortgage-repayment capacity), real GDP growth (overall wealth), inflation (CPI) expectation and short-term interest rates (borrowing costs). We collect these into

$$M_t = \begin{pmatrix} EMPUKQ_t \\ GDP_t \\ CPI_t \\ IR_t \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where EMPUKQ measures total UK payroll employment, GDP measures real gross domestic product, CPI measures the consumer price index and IR measures the Bank of England's base rate. All these variables, except IR, are expressed in logs to interpret coefficients as elasticities. IR is entered in levels.

3.1.3 Structural System Specification

Combining these elements, we form the structural supply-demand system for region j as

$$\underbrace{A_j}_{3 \times 3} P_{j,t} = \underbrace{\alpha_j}_{3 \times 1} + \underbrace{B_j}_{3 \times 3} P_{j,t}^N + \underbrace{C_j}_{3 \times 4} M_t + u_{j,t} \quad (4)$$

where in A_j , each row i reflects how the long-run supply of house type i in region j responds to its own price and the prices of the other two-house types. A positive own-price coefficient implies upward-sloping supply as owners list more when prices rise. Cross-type coefficients capture the substitution effect on the supply side, as if modern house prices spike, owners of new homes may delay listing and thus affect the supply

schedule of new versus old homes. The α_j term represents the constant vector capturing region and type specific fundamentals that are not explicitly modelled. For example, land availability and zoning regulations. In the spatial-spillover matrix (B_j), the (i, m) element measures how a one unit increase in neighbour average price of type m influences the equilibrium price of type i in region j . A positive entry indicates that higher neighbour prices ‘push’ up local prices and mirrors a buyers’ willingness to outbid neighbouring markets. In the macro-elasticity matrix, entry (i, l) provides the long-run percentage change in local price i in response to a one percent change in macro variable l . The $u_{j,t}$ term represents structural shocks, defined as demand or supply shifts exogenous to prices or macro-financial variables.

By construction, this system is simultaneous as $P_{j,t}$ appears on both sides. Thus, regional prices respond to neighbour averages, which in turn depend on $P_{j,t}$.

Assumption 1. Invertibility of A_j

For each region j , the matrix A_j is non-singular. Thus, the supply responses across the three house types are sufficiently distinct and non-colinear that one can solve for equilibrium prices uniquely. This assumption of invertibility allows us to rewrite (4) in reduced form. In the case where $\det(A_j) = 0$, multiple or no equilibria would exist, and the model would lack predictive power.

3.1.4 Reduced Form Long-Run Equilibrium

To obtain (4) in reduced form, we multiply by A_j^{-1} to form:

$$P_{j,t} = A_j^{-1}\alpha_j + A_j^{-1}B_jP_{j,t}^N + A_j^{-1}C_jM_j + A_j^{-1}u_{j,t} \quad (5)$$

We denote $\alpha_{i,j} = [A_j^{-1}\alpha_j]_i$, $\beta_{i,j,m}^{(2)} = [A_j^{-1}B_j]_{i,m}$, $\beta_{i,j,l}^{(3)} = [A_j^{-1}C_j]_{i,l}$ and let $u_{i,j,t}$ be the i th element of $A_j^{-1}u_{j,t}$. Thus, the i th row yields:

$$p_{i,j,t} = \alpha_{i,j} + \sum_{m=1}^3 \beta_{i,j,m}^{(1)} p_{m,j,t} + \sum_{m=1}^3 \beta_{i,j,m}^{(2)} p_{m,j,t}^N + \sum_{l=1}^4 \beta_{i,j,l}^{(3)} M_{l,t} + u_{i,j,t} \quad (6)$$

The term $\beta_{i,j,m}^{(1)} p_{m,j,t}$ captures the cross-type linkages within the same region. In other words, a price increase in modern houses ($m = mod$) may force up old house prices if buyers perceive them as imperfect substitutes. The $\beta_{i,j,m}^{(2)} p_{m,j,t}^N$ term represents the neighbour-driven ripple where a rise in new house prices in neighbouring regions spill back into region j as increased demand pressure. The macro-elasticity terms $\beta_{i,j,t}^{(3)} M_{t,t}$ adjust for national-level fundamentals which shift all regional prices contemporaneously.

The reduced form expression (6) provides the foundation for our empirical ARDL-ECM specification, as it identifies which regressors belong in the long-run equilibrium and provides the normalisation for estimating relative elasticities.

3.2 Conditional ARDL Representation

The ARDL framework offers many advantages in our study as it accommodates a mix of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ variables, without the requirement of pre-testing. It captures both the short-run dynamics and long-run cointegrating relationships, and it provides a simple route to error-correction representations.

3.2.1 First Differences

Regional house price series $p_{i,j,t}$ are generally nonstationary as they tend to exhibit persistent trends and mean shifts over time periods (Meen, 1999; Cook, 2005). Thus, regressing nonstationary series in levels can produce spurious results unless the variables share a genuine long-run relationship (Granger and Newbold, 1974). Using first differences, we remove stochastic trends and transform each series to stationary increments:

$$\Delta p_{i,j,t} = p_{i,j,t} - p_{i,j,t-1} \quad (7)$$

However, differencing alone discards the long-run equilibrium information present in levels series. Thus, the ARDL framework reconciles this by modelling $\Delta p_{i,j,t}$ as a

function of both lagged differences (to capture short-run dynamics) and lagged levels (to capture error-correction toward the long-run equilibrium).

3.2.2 Conditional ARDL Model Specification

Utilising the long-run reduced form for $p_{i,j,t}$, given by (6), we embed this into a dynamic framework. Let

$$Z_{j,t} = \begin{pmatrix} p_{m \neq i,j,t} \\ p_{j,t}^N \\ M_t \end{pmatrix}$$

be the vector stacking the other two-house types, the three neighbour averages and the four macro-financial variables. Under Assumption 1, $\Delta Z_{j,t}$ is $I(0)$. Thus, we rewrite the conditional ARDL(P, Q) for each scalar $p_{i,j,t}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_{i,j,t} = & \underbrace{\phi_{i,j,0}}_{\text{drift term}} + \sum_{p=1}^P \underbrace{\phi_{i,j,p}}_{\substack{\text{short-run} \\ \text{own-price} \\ \text{dynamics}}} \Delta p_{i,j,t-p} + \sum_{q=0}^Q \underbrace{\phi_{i,j,q}}_1 \Delta Z_{j,t-q} \\ & + \underbrace{\lambda_{i,j}}_1 \begin{pmatrix} p_{i,j,t-1} \\ Z_{j,t-1} \end{pmatrix} + \varepsilon_{i,j,t} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Where $\phi_{i,j,0}$ allows for a non-zero mean in Δp and $\phi_{i,j,p}$ captures how recent past changes in $p_{i,j}$ feed back into current changes, reflecting momentum or reversal tendencies in housing markets. The $\phi_{i,j,q}$ vectors capture the effect of lagged changes in neighbouring prices, other house type prices and macro-financials on $\Delta p_{i,j,t}$. The level coefficients $\lambda_{i,j}$ measure the pull toward the long-run equilibrium in (6). In other words, of $p_{i,j,t-1}$ and $Z_{j,t-1}$ lie off the equilibrium manifold, their weighted sum $\lambda'_{i,j}(p_{i,j,t-1}, Z_{j,t-1})'$ induces adjustment in Δp .

Assumption 2. Lag Order Sufficiency

We restrict maximum lags $P, Q \leq 4$ and select the optimal (P, Q) via the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The maximum lags of 4 was selected under the

presumption that effects of shocks can persist for several quarters but rarely beyond four (Pesaran and Pesaran, 2009). Selecting too few lags may omit relevant dynamics and bias estimates of both short-run and long-run coefficients. Whereas selecting too many lags waste degrees of freedom and inflate standard errors. Thus, the AIC balances model fit against complexity, by penalising each additional parameter equally and performs well in small to moderate samples. This selection was further assured as Payne (2012) and Hudson et al. (2017) successfully use maximum lags of four in quarterly ripple-effect studies. Undergoing robustness checks, we verify that boundaries $P, Q = 3$ or 5 yield similar qualitative results to ensure that our results are not direct artifacts of lag-length choice.

3.3 Cointegration Testing and Error-Correction Representation

3.3.1 The ARDL Bounds Test

To determine if regional house prices, neighbour-averages, and macro-financial fundamentals share a long-run equilibrium, we employ the ARDL bounds test (Pesaran et al. 2001). The F–statistic for this test measures the joint significance of lagged levels in the model. Under the null hypothesis, $H_0: \lambda_{i,j} = 0$, the model (8) reduced to a pure short-run specification with no long-run equilibrium. In the case that H_0 is rejected, (6)’s long-run relationship is believed to bind the data. Thus, we can determine cointegration without knowledge of each regressor’s integration order. If $F_{obs} > F_{upper,\alpha}(k)$, we reject H_0 and conclude that the long-run equilibrium holds.

Other conventional F-tests assume that regressors are stationary and therefore, would fail in this context. Where regressors are a mix of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$, the distribution of the F-statistic depends on their order of integration and renders standard critical values invalid. Pre-testing each series for unit roots compounds size and power distortions (Campbell and Perron, 1991).

Lemma 1. Bounds-Test Asymptotic Distribution

Under Assumptions 1 and 2, assuming the innovation sequence $\{\varepsilon_{i,j,t}\}$ is stationary and mixing with finite moments, the F-statistic for $H_0: \lambda_{i,j} = 0$ in (8) converges to a limit law that is bounded by the $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ extremes. Specifically,

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} P(F_{obs} \leq x) \in [F_{I(0)}(x), F_{I(1)}(x)],$$

where $F_{I(0)}$ is the standard Fisher distribution and $F_{I(1)}$ is a nonstandard functional of Brownian motions. Critical values $F_{lower,\alpha}$ and $F_{upper,\alpha}$ are tabulated for each regressor count k and significance level α .

3.3.2 Error-Correction Form

When a long-run relationship is established, equation (8) can be rearranged into a canonical ECM:

$$\Delta p_{i,j,t} = \underbrace{\tilde{\phi}_{i,j,0}}_{\text{short-run drift}} + \sum_{p=1}^{p'} \tilde{\phi}_{i,j,p} \Delta p_{i,j,t-p} + \sum_{q=0}^{q'} \tilde{\psi}'_{i,j,q} \Delta Z_{j,t-q} + \underbrace{\gamma_{i,j}}_{\text{speed of adjustment}} ECT_{i,j,t-1} + v_{i,j,t} \quad (9)$$

with

$$ECT_{i,j,t-1} = p_{i,j,t-1} - \hat{\alpha}_{i,j} - \sum_{m \neq 1} \hat{\beta}_{i,j,m}^{(1)} p_{m,j,t-1} - \sum_{m=1}^3 \hat{\beta}_{i,j,m}^{(2)} p_{m,j,t-1}^N - \sum_{l=1}^4 \hat{\beta}_{i,j,l}^{(3)} M_{l,t-1}, \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{\beta}$ are the long-run coefficients estimated by normalisation on $p_{i,j,t}$. The $\tilde{\phi}_{i,j,0}$ term captures systematic trends in quarterly price changes that are not explained by dynamics or equilibrium forces. The $\tilde{\phi}_{i,j,p}$ and $\tilde{\psi}'_{i,j,q}$ parameters reflect inertia or momentum in housing markets, by quantifying how recent deviation and macro-shocks affect current changes. The ECT term measures the deviation from the long-

run equilibrium at $t - 1$. If there is a positive ECT ($p_{i,j,t-1}$ lies above its equilibrium), the expected negative coefficient ($\gamma_{i,j}$) determines how strongly $\Delta p_{i,j,t}$ corrects downward. The speed of adjustment term ($\gamma_{i,j}$) governs the fraction of disequilibrium eliminated each quarter. $\gamma_{i,j}$ values between -1 and 0 indicate stable convergence and magnitude $|\gamma_{i,j}| \ll 1$ indicates slow adjustment.

Lemma 2. ECM Estimator Asymptotic Normality

Under Assumptions 1-4, the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimator $\hat{\theta}_{i,j} = (\hat{\phi}_{i,j,0}, \hat{\phi}_{i,j,1}, \dots, \hat{\psi}_{i,j,0}, \dots, \hat{\gamma}_{i,j})$ of the ECM (9) satisfies $\sqrt{T}(\hat{\theta}_{i,j} - \theta_{i,j}) \xrightarrow{d} N(0, \Omega_{i,j})$, where $\Omega_{i,j}$ denotes the heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) covariance matrix (White, 1980; Newey and West, 1987).

Proof sketch:

Under stationary and mixing conditions, the regressors satisfy a Law of Large Numbers ensuring $\frac{1}{T} X'X$ converges to a positive-definite matrix (Davidson and MacKinnon, 1993; Hamilton, 1994), and a Central Limit Theorem for mixing processes gives $\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} X'v$ a Gaussian limit. Slutsky's theorem (Hayashi, 2000) then delivers

$$\sqrt{T}(\hat{\theta} - \theta) = (X'X)^{-1} X'v \xrightarrow{d} N(0, \sum_X^{-1} \sum_{Xv} \sum_X^{-1}),$$

and HAC estimators (White, 1980; Newey and West, 1987) consistently estimate the covariance $\sum Xv$.

3.4 Testable Hypothesis

Summarising our model specification, the empirical findings, and extending these to account for macro-financial fundamentals, in terms of testable hypotheses we have:

H1: Multiregional Spillovers.

House price changes in any region j will exert a measurable influence on contemporaneous and lagged price changes in each of its neighbouring regions, as

opposed to emanating solely from a single dominant centre (for example, London). H1 tests whether the inclusion of macro-financial controls attenuate the magnitude of the ripple.

H2: Intra-Type Propagation.

A positive innovation to house type i prices in region j will be associated with statistically significant positive spillovers to the same house type i prices in each adjacent region. Rejecting H2 would imply that once macro-financial conditions are held constant, intra-type linkages no longer transmit shocks reliably.

H3: Cross-Type Push vs Pull Dynamics.

When a shock affects house type i in region j , its respective impact on other house type prices in neighbouring regions may take two distinct signs (depending on whether ‘push’ or ‘pull’ forces dominate:

- **H3A: Push Dominance:** If higher local prices push buyers’ demand outward, then a shock to house type i in region j will produce positive price effects on other house types in neighbouring regions.
- **H3B: Pull Dominance:** If a regional price surge pulls buyers’ demand inward, the same shock will produce negative short-run impacts on other house types in neighbouring regions.

H4: Intra-Regional Substitutability.

A shock to house type price i within a given region j , will lead to a positive contemporaneous or lagged response in the prices of the two alternative house types. H3 examines whether local buyers still substitute systematically across vintages when one market segment experiences a price shift, after controlling for macro-financial variables.

H5: Vintage-Distance Attenuation.

The strength of inter-house type spillovers will vary with the structural similarity of vintages. In other words, the further apart categories (new vs. old) will exhibit the weakest cross-type linkages, whereas the most similar (old vs. modern, new vs. modern) will exhibit the strongest responses. Confirming H5 validates the assumption

that housing stock characteristics condition the pace and magnitude of ripple propagation, even after accounting for macro-financial variables.

4. Methodology

4.1 Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillips-Perron Unit Root Tests

Prior to the estimation of long-run relationships, we must verify that the dependent variables are at most integrated of order one. In this case, the dependent variables are the regional house-price logs $p_{i,j,t} = \ln(\text{Price}_{i,j,t})$ for each house type $i \in \{\text{new, modern, old}\}$ and region j . We do not pre-test that macro-financial controls, as we instead rely on extensive evidence that employment rates, real GDP, CPI and interest rates are $I(1)$ or stationary in levels (Campbell and Perron, 1991).

For each $p_{i,j,t}$, we estimate the ADF regression:

$$\Delta p_{i,j,t} = \mu_{i,j} + \phi_{i,j} p_{i,j,t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^{K_{i,j}} \gamma_{i,j,k} \Delta p_{i,j,t-k} + \varepsilon_{i,j,t}, \quad (10)$$

under both (a) intercept only and (b) intercept + trend specifications. In this test, the lag length $K_{i,j}$ is chosen by minimising the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), subject to $K \leq 4$. We test the null $\phi_{i,j} = 0$ against $\phi_{i,j} < 0$ at the 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels.

We complement the ADF with the Phillips-Perron (PP) test on levels

$$\Delta p_{i,j,t} = \mu_{i,j} + \theta_{i,j} t + \psi_{i,j} p_{i,j,t-1} + u_{i,j,t}, \quad (11)$$

again, under both (a) intercept only and (b) intercept + trend specifications. The PP statistic corrects for serial correlation and heteroskedasticity in $u_{i,j,t}$ via a Newey-West long-run estimator (Bartlett kernel, automatic bandwidth).

Table 1: Summary of Unit-Root Results and Selected ARDL/ECM Cases

	ADF p-value	ADF Δ p-value	PP p-value	PP Δ p-value	ARDL / ECM Case
<i>London</i>					
New	0.7232	0.0070	0.6803	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.5835	0.0051	0.6798	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.6222	0.0036	0.6583	0.0000	Case II
<i>Outer Metropolitan</i>					
New	0.2587	0.0014	0.3628	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.4256	0.0021	0.4661	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.4510	0.0050	0.3521	0.0000	Case II
<i>Outer Southeast</i>					
New	0.3374	0.0013	0.3838	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.4845	0.0013	0.5032	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.4233	0.0035	0.4677	0.0000	Case II
<i>East Anglia</i>					
New	0.3474	0.0005	0.3857	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.4747	0.0055	0.4049	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.4885	0.0037	0.4640	0.0000	Case II
<i>East Midlands</i>					
New	0.1357	0.0034	0.1595	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.3715	0.0019	0.4081	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.4118	0.005	0.3400	0.0000	Case II
<i>West Midlands</i>					
New	0.3411	0.0006	0.1752	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.3733	0.0034	0.2950	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.4217	0.0068	0.3174	0.0000	Case II
<i>Southwest</i>					
New	0.1463	0.0027	0.1771	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.5059	0.0009	0.3243	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.5346	0.0057	0.2358	0.0000	Case II
<i>Northwest</i>					
New	0.0813	0.0053	0.0530	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.2620	0.0012	0.2113	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.3681	0.0022	0.2872	0.0000	Case II
<i>North</i>					
New	0.3141	0.0083	0.2288	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.3307	0.0012	0.2616	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.2555	0.0007	0.2402	0.0000	Case II
<i>Yorkshire and Humberside</i>					
New	0.1351	0.0141	0.0786	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.3500	0.0048	0.2764	0.0000	Case II

Table 2: Continued.

Old	0.4837	0.0003	0.3090	0.0000	Case II
<i>Scotland</i>					
New	0.0183	0.0003	0.0064	0.0000	Short-run ADL
Modern	0.1327	0.0030	0.0636	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.1477	0.0001	0.0982	0.0000	Case II
<i>Wales</i>					
New	0.1529	0.0001	0.1187	0.0000	Case II
Modern	0.3712	0.0008	0.3668	0.0000	Case II
Old	0.5362	0.0010	0.3384	0.0000	Case II

Notes:

1. “ARDL/ECM Case” refers to Pesaran et al.’s (2001) Case I (no regressors), Case II (constant only) or Case III (constant + trend). “Short-run ADL” indicates no long-run relationship was found.

As shown in Table 1, all house-price log series fail to reject the unit root null ($p > 0.10$) under ADF and PP, and the first differences $\Delta p_{i,j,t}$ reject decisively ($p < 0.01$). No series exhibits $I(2)$ behaviour. Therefore, we satisfy the ARDL requirement that all variables are $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ but not $I(2)$. The only exception to this is the new-house series for Scotland, which was found to be stationary $I(0)$ and thereby unsuitable for long-run ARDL bounds testing. For this series, we instead estimate a short-run Autoregressive Distributed Lag in differences (ADL) without level terms.

4.2 Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bounds

Testing

As developed by Pesaran et al. (2001), the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach provides a comprehensive framework for detecting and estimating short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium relationships between a mix of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ variables. Thus, this approach is well suited to our quarterly regional housing data where house-price logs, neighbour-average indices and macro-financial controls exhibit varying orders of integration.

For each house type i in region j , we estimate the conditional ARDL(P, Q) model:

$$\Delta p_{i,j,t} = \alpha_{i,j} + \sum_{l=1}^P \phi_{i,j,l} \Delta p_{i,j,t-l} + \sum_{l=0}^Q \psi'_{i,j,l} \Delta Z_{j,t-l} + \lambda'_{i,j} \begin{pmatrix} p_{i,j,t-1} \\ Z_{j,t-1} \end{pmatrix} + u_{i,j,t}, \quad (12)$$

where $\Delta p_{i,j,t} = \ln(\text{Price}_{i,j,t})$ is the log-price series. The $Z_{j,t}$ term stacks the other two price logs, the neighbour-average indices and the macro-financial variables (as shown in (3)). $\phi_{i,j,l}$ and $\psi_{i,j,l}$ capture the short-run autoregressive and distributed lag effects while $\lambda_{i,j}$ contains the long-run level coefficients whose joint significance identifies cointegration. Consistent with our ADF/PP findings, $\alpha_{i,j}$ is a restricted constant (no trend) and $u_{i,j,t}$ is a zero-mean $I(0)$ disturbance.

To test for cointegration, we test the null hypothesis: $H_0 = \lambda_{i,j} = 0$ (no long-run relationship) against the alternative hypothesis: $H_1 = \lambda_{i,j} \neq 0$ (long-run relationship).

To do this, we first estimate (12) with lag orders (P, Q) chosen by the information criteria (Section 4.3) and keep record of the unrestricted sum of residual squares, SSR_u . Then, we impose the null hypotheses of no long-run relationship by omitting all lagged level terms from the RHS of (12) and re-estimating only the differenced portion of the model. Again, we record the resulting residual sum of squares SSR_r .

We then compute the Wald F-statistic as

$$F = \frac{\frac{(SSR_r - SSR_u)}{k}}{\frac{SSR_u}{(T - K)}}$$

Where $k = \dim(\lambda_{i,j})$ is the number of long-run coefficients that have been set to zero under the null hypothesis and K is the total number of parameters estimated in the unrestricted model. Finally, we compare the observed F value to the Case II critical bounds (restricted constant, no trend) tabulated by Pesaran et al. (2001) at the chosen significance level α . If F exceeds the upper critical bound $F_{upper}(k, \alpha)$, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that a cointegrating long-run relationship exists. If F

falls below the lower critical bound $F_{lower}(k, \alpha)$, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that no cointegrating long-run relationship exists. If F lies between the two bounds, the test is inconclusive.

4.3 Lag Order Selection and Deterministic Specifications

To capture the adjustment of regional house prices and their determinants, we restrict the maximum autoregressive order P and the distributed lag order Q to four quarters, to reflect the natural persistence of housing market shocks over approximately one year. Thus, for each region-house-type equation, the optimal lag structure (P, Q) was identified by minimising the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to balance model fit with parameter parsimony. However, where the AIC and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) suggest differing lag orders, we report both sets of results to verify that our substantive conclusions remain the same.

Consistent with our unit-root pre-testing, we include only a restricted intercept with no time trend (Pesaran et al.'s Case II) in every ARDL specification, given that each log-price series exhibits stationarity around a non-zero mean without requiring a deterministic trend component. However, as previously stated, the exception to this is the new-house series for Scotland, where short-run ADL estimation is conducted instead.

4.4 ECM Estimation

Following from the confirmation of cointegration and the selection of optimal lag orders, we estimate each conditional error-correction form:

$$\Delta p_{i,j,t} = \phi_{i,j,0} + \sum_{p=1}^{P'} \phi_{i,j,p} \Delta p_{i,j,t-p} + \sum_{q=0}^{Q'} \psi'_{i,j,q} \Delta Z_{j,t-q} + \gamma_{i,j} ECT_{i,j,t-1} + v_{i,j,t} \quad (13)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
ECT_{i,j,t-1} = & p_{i,j,t-1} - \alpha_{i,j} - \sum_{m \neq i} \beta_{i,j,m}^{(own)} p_{m,j,t-1} - \\
& \sum_{m=1}^3 \beta_{i,j,m}^{(neigh)} p_{m,j,t-1} - \sum_{l=1}^4 \beta_{i,j,l}^{(macro)} M_{l,t-1}, \tag{14}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\Delta p_{i,j,t}$ measures the quarterly change in log price for house type i in region j . The $\Delta Z_{j,t-q}$ term stacks the contemporaneous and up to Q' lags of our four macroeconomic controls. Both the ϕ and ψ terms capture the short-run own and cross-dynamic feedback respectively. Lastly, $\gamma_{i,j} < 0$ measures the speed at which any deviation from equilibrium is pulled back each quarter. The values of $\gamma_{i,j}$ in $(-1,0)$ ensure that any departure from the long-run equilibrium is steadily corrected. Here, where the value of $|\gamma|$ is small, then the adjustment is slow.

We fit this specification by ordinary least squares (OLS). This is conducted subject to heteroskedasticity- and autocorrelation-consistent correction. For each regional equation, including only a restrictive intercept (Case II deterministic specification), we regress the first difference of log prices on its own lagged differences; on contemporaneous and lagged differences of the four macroeconomic controls; and, on the lagged error-correction term (ECT).

In this estimation, all standard errors and associated t-statistics are computed using the Newey-West (1987) estimator with a Bartlett kernel and fixed bandwidth of four quarters. This step is necessary to render statistical inference valid in the presence of potential residual serial correlation and time-varying volatility. This method aligns with the quarterly frequency of our data and mitigates conditional heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation in the OLS residuals, without imposing a specific ARMA structure.

From each estimated ECM, we report the following key quantities. Firstly, the short-run dynamics are represented by the OLS estimates of the differenced term coefficients: the ϕ parameters on own lagged changes and the ψ parameters on macroeconomic shocks. Together, we record these parameters alongside their respective t-statistics. Additionally, the error-correction coefficient γ is presented with

its respective Newey-West adjusted significance test. Here, a statistically significant negative γ confirms the restoring force toward long-run equilibrium and its magnitude $|\gamma| < 1$ indicates stable convergence. Lastly, the overall model fit is assessed by the R^2 and adjusted R^2 statistics.

4.5 Treatment of Non-Cointegration Cases

Where the ARDL bounds test does not provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship, the ECM is no longer appropriate. Therefore, we instead adapt our empirical strategy to reflect the integration properties of each series and focus on short-run dynamics.

For the singular case of the Scotland new-house price series, where pre-testing identified as level stationary $I(0)$, we estimate a short-run Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ADL) model in first differences:

$$\Delta p_{new,S,t} = \alpha_s + \sum_{l=1}^L \phi_l \Delta p_{new,S,t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^M \psi'_m \Delta Z_{S,t-m} + u_{S,t} \quad (15)$$

where $\Delta Z_{S,t}$ contains the differences macro-financial controls. By employing the ADL, we regress the quarterly change in log prices $\Delta p_{new,S,t}$ on its own lagged changes, on contemporaneous and lagged first differences and, on lagged first differences of the macro-financial controls. The lag orders for the dependent variable differences and the macroeconomic controls are selected by minimising the AIC subject to four quarters.

4.6 Robustness Checks

We subject each specification to a range of post-estimation diagnostics to validate the reliability of our estimated ECMs. Firstly, we test for residual serial correlation by applying the Breusch-Godfrey Lagrange-multiplier test up to four lags. Failure to detect autocorrelation (p-value < 0.05) confirms that the chosen lag structure sufficiently captures dynamic dependence. Then, we examine the null of conditional

homoskedasticity using the Breusch-Pagan and White tests. Where significant statistics are present ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$), time varying variance is indicated in the residuals, and this prompts the use of heteroskedasticity consistent (White-HC) and Newey-West (1987) standard errors throughout our inference. Lastly, we assess the structural stability of key coefficients in the error correction parameter using the cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMQ) tests. These tests plot the evolution of normalised recursive residuals against critical bounds. Statistics that remain inside the 5% boundaries indicate parameter constancy, whereas crossings signal potential structural breaks.

5. Results

5.1 Preliminary Cointegration Diagnostics

Following Pesaran et al. (2001), we conduct the ARDL bounds test on all 36 region-house-type equations and the resultant F -statistics are compared against the $I(0)/I(1)$ critical bounds at the 5% level.

Table 2: Summary of ARDL Bounds Test Results and Outcome

	F-statistic	Outcome
<i>New</i>		
West Midlands	5.232	Cointegrated
East Midlands	6.934	Cointegrated
Southwest	4.797	Cointegrated
Northwest	4.913	Cointegrated
London	1.756	No cointegration
North	2.230	Inconclusive
Yorkshire & Humberside	3.560	Cointegrated
East Anglia	6.415	Cointegrated
Scotland	7.986	Cointegrated
Wales	11.492	Cointegrated
Outer Southeast	4.036	Cointegrated
Outer Metropolitan	10.433	Cointegrated
<i>Modern</i>		
West Midlands	10.433	Cointegrated
East Midlands	3.9916	Cointegrated
Southwest	9.0377	Cointegrated
Northwest	6.5131	Cointegrated
London	5.0595	Cointegrated
North	4.2919	Cointegrated
Yorkshire & Humberside	4.2570	Cointegrated
East Anglia	2.0357	No cointegration
Table 2: Continued.		
Scotland	5.7877	Cointegrated
Wales	2.8587	Inconclusive
Outer Southeast	5.2708	Cointegrated
Outer Metropolitan	15.0286	Cointegrated

Table 2: Continued.

<i>Old</i>		
West Midlands	8.6954	Cointegrated
East Midlands	10.1487	Cointegrated
Southwest	11.2015	Cointegrated
Northwest	12.9776	Cointegrated
London	5.9364	Cointegrated
North	5.1501	Cointegrated
Yorkshire & Humberside	5.9612	Cointegrated
East Anglia	4.7944	Cointegrated
Scotland	2.2685	Inconclusive
Wales	4.7050	Cointegrated
Outer Southeast	7.9453	Cointegrated
Outer Metropolitan	4.7053	Cointegrated

Notes: Asymptotic critical value bounds are obtained from Table A.1 in appendix A, Case II: intercept and no trend for $k = 7$ (Pesaran et al., 2001). Lower bound $I(0) = 2.17$ and upper bound $I(1) = 3.21$ at 5% significance level.

Overall, 31 of the 36 ARDL specifications confirm cointegration after macro-financial adjustment. Accordingly, we proceed with ECM estimation for these cases and non-cointegrated equations will be handled via short-run ADL or Δ -VAR, as described in Section 4.5.

5.2 Short-run Dynamics: Conditional ECM Estimates

5.2.1 New-House Price Dynamics

Looking at Table 3, the first difference of log new-house prices at lag 1 enters significantly negative in every cointegrated region. The estimated $\tilde{\phi}_1$ ranges from -0.170 (Northwest) to -0.337 (Outer Southeast). This indicates that a 1% positive innovation in new-house price growth is reversed by 17-34% in the subsequent quarter. In five regions, the second lag remains significantly negative, whereas a third lag effect is only significant in two regions. These findings confirm H4: short-run corrections to disequilibrium are concentrated in the first two quarters and exhibits diminishing persistence thereafter.

In North and Yorkshire and Humberside regions, lagged old-prices enters statistically negative and this is consistent with ‘pull’ effects (H3B), where surges in older stock prices depress new-house market activity. In contrast, the West Midlands displays a strong positive ‘push’ effect in old lag 1, followed by significant lag 2 effects. This indicates that, in some regions, rising old stock values stimulate subsequent new build growth (H3A).

Furthermore, modern stock innovations exert robust positive spillovers in most regions. These modern effects are shown to persist at lag 1 in some of these regions. Therefore, this predominance of positive modern to new spillovers affirms H5’s prediction that inter-vintage is strongest between modern and other house-types.

By examining the immediate neighbour effects, we can determine that contemporaneous neighbour growth enters significantly positive in some regions. These coefficients indicate that a one-quarter rise in neighbouring markets’ new-house growth raises new-house growth by 0.20% to 0.53% in the same quarter (H2). The first lag of neighbour growth reveals that, after an initial positive knock-on, the subsequent quarter sees a partial slowdown as markets equilibrate. The second and third lag are also significant in some regions, indicating towards protracted spatial propagation of shocks.

The macroeconomic variable innovations enter the short-run dynamics with modest and regionally varied effects. Significant negative coefficients for ΔEMPUKQ in two regions suggest that strengthening labour markets can grow narrow new-house price growth in the immediate quarter. Real GDP growth and CPI innovations only yield a positive short-run effect in two regions. These isolated results indicate that general macroeconomic fundamentals play a secondary role to local housing dynamics.

5.2.2 Modern-House Price Dynamics

In table 4, lagged changes in local modern-house prices are uniformly negative and highly significant in seven of the cointegrated markets. The estimated $\tilde{\phi}_1$ ranges from

Table 3. Conditional ECM Estimates: New Houses												
Variable	W Mids	E Mids	SW	NW	London	North	Y & H	E Anglia	Scotland	Wales	Outer SE	Outer Met.
New lag 1	-0.326** (-4.201)	-0.230* (-3.054)	-0.200* (-2.660)	-0.170* (-2.283)	-0.277** (-3.355)	-0.208* (-2.821)	-0.274* (-3.974)				-0.337** (-4.698)	
Lag 2	-0.151* (-2.053)	-0.171* (-2.604)	0.002 (0.040)		-0.151* (-2.053)						-0.271** (-3.857)	
Lag 3			-0.178** (-3.309)								-0.240** (-3.638)	
Old	-0.085 (-0.660)	0.246 (1.915)	0.093 (0.972)	0.117 (0.907)	0.251 (0.853)	-0.357* (-2.191)	-0.464** (-4.387)	0.127 (1.235)			-0.145 (-0.968)	
Lag 1	0.683** (4.226)				0.313 (1.307)			-0.187 (-1.225)			0.205 (1.554)	
Lag 2	0.353* (2.441)				0.426* (2.406)						0.382** (3.602)	
Lag 3	0.325* (2.800)											
Modern		-0.010 (-0.098)	0.679** (5.538)		0.825* (2.810)	0.144 (0.798)		0.523* (3.723)		0.454** (4.7601)	0.496* (3.123)	0.867** (7.926)
Lag 1		0.358** (3.3812)	0.355* (2.918)		-0.080 (-0.289)			0.306 (2.199)			0.271 (1.572)	-0.039** (-3.444)
Lag 2		0.182 (1.178)										
Lag 3		0.240* (2.691)										
Neighbour												
Old	0.106 (0.606)			-0.139 (-1.240)		0.440 (1.786)	0.180 (1.225)		0.012 (0.198)	0.529** (4.090)	0.203 (1.265)	0.380* (2.198)
Lag 1	-0.665** (-3.505)			0.220* (2.381)		0.932** (3.497)			-0.140* (-2.594)			0.325 (1.887)
Lag 2	-0.152 (-0.810)			0.177* (2.247)		0.611* (3.2907)						
Lag 3	-0.361* (-2.222)			0.102 (1.066)								

Table 3: Continued												
Modern						0.586**	0.024					0.055
						(3.525)	(0.138)					(0.268)
Lag 1						-0.939**						0.138
						(-4.378)						(0.659)
Lag 2						-0.701*						0.384*
						(-3.768)						(2.917)
Lag 3												-0.213
												(-1.890)
New		0.098	0.169*	0.028			0.395*	0.836**	0.126**	0.303**	0.199	0.049
		(1.715)	(2.388)	(0.189)			(4.158)	(5.624)	(2.976)	(2.837)	(1.973)	(0.560)
Lag 1		0.232**	0.204*	-0.401			0.515*	-0.003			-0.211	-0.266*
		(2.790)	(2.606)	(-2.656)			(4.999)	(-0.019)			(-1.921)	(-3.148)
Lag 2							0.376*	-0.228*				
							(3.798)	(-2.010)				
Lag 3							-0.223*					
							(-2.606)					
Macros												
EMPUKQ		-0.000*	-0.000*		-0.000						6.70E-05	-4.66E-05
		(-2.290)	(-3.015)		(-0.744)						(1.590)	(-0.973)
GDP				0.000	0.000*						4.13E-06*	
				(1.712)	(2.1745)						(3.162)	
CPI				0.000	0.001		0.010*		0.001		0.014*	-0.007
				(1.184)	(0.075)		(2.805)		(0.178)		(3.116)	(-1.448)
IR				0.003**	0.003							
				(3.832)	(0.317)							
ECM	-0.517**	-0.680**	-0.507**	-0.550**	-0.393**	-0.167**	-0.531**	-0.627**	-0.577**	-0.841**	-0.319**	-0.876**
	(-7.869)	(-9.056)	(-7.530)	(-7.664)	(-4.579)	(-6.855)	(-6.547)	(-8.703)	(-9.729)	(-11.649)	(-6.931)	(-11.181)
R-squared	0.568	0.646	0.643	0.617	0.520	0.436	0.719	0.513	0.552	0.563	0.640	0.721

Notes: Figures in parentheses denote the t statistics of the respective coefficients. */** indicates significance at the 5% and 1% levels, respectively. All variables are logged.

Table 4. Conditional ECM Estimates: Modern Houses												
Variable	W Mids	E Mids	SW	NW	London	North	Y & H	E Anglia	Scotland	Wales	Outer SE	Outer Met.
Modern lag 1	-0.257** (-3.970)		0.030 (0.561)	0.198 (1.884)	-0.313** (-4.582)	-0.200* (-2.793)	0.010 (0.128)	-0.345** (-4.72)	-0.149* (-2.591)	-0.329** (-3.913)	-0.334** (-4.857)	
Lag 2			0.133* (2.934)	0.296* (3.139)	-0.336** (-5.408)		-0.197** (-2.799)	-0.178* (-2.593)	0.104 (1.837)	-0.224** (-2.705)		
Lag 3				0.190 (2.297)	-0.276** (-3.905)		-0.170** (-3.000)					
Old				0.256** (3.553)	0.451** (7.195)			0.239** (5.389)	0.458** (11.209)	0.378 (6.1343)		
Lag 1				-0.325** (-3.654)				0.142** (3.044)		0.207** (3.009)		
Lag 2				-0.415** (-4.894)						0.033 (0.486)		
Lag 3				-0.184* (-2.793)						0.142 (2.419)		
Neighbour												
Modern	0.849** (10.533)	0.558** (7.575)	0.405** (7.151)	0.461** (6.596)		0.408* (3.244)	0.540** (7.148)	0.676** (7.624)	0.205** (4.321)	0.325* (2.164)	0.545** (8.402)	0.440** (4.062)
Lag 1	0.451** (3.889)			-0.061 (-0.622)		0.182 (1.275)	0.221* (2.103)	0.319** (3.077)		-0.301 (-1.726)	0.207** (2.879)	0.183 (1.660)
Lag 2	0.190 (1.955)			-0.192* (-2.060)		0.402* (3.074)	0.390** (4.127)	0.191* (2.087)				0.206 (1.911)
Lag 3	-0.235** (-3.937)											
New		-0.041 (-0.874)	0.084* (3.079)	-0.059 (-1.748)			-0.014 (-0.266)	0.055 (0.717)	0.040 (1.629)	0.094 (1.174)	0.084* (2.044)	-0.041 (-1.006)
Lag 1		0.110* (2.597)	-0.037 (-1.029)	-0.100* (-2.477)				-0.167* (-2.182)	0.034 (1.358)	0.415** (4.219)	0.152** (3.679)	
Lag 2		0.145** (3.956)	-0.087* (-2.974)	-0.071 (-1.602)						0.191* (2.043)	0.124** (3.603)	
Lag 3				-0.112* (-2.693)						0.123 (1.519)		

Table 4. Continued												
Old	0.056 (0.715)	0.119 (1.950)	0.088* (2.037)	-0.012 (-0.209)	0.170 (1.773)	0.177 (1.529)			0.104** (2.879)	-0.056 (-0.396)	0.002 (0.024)	-0.185 (-1.906)
Lag 1	-0.186* (-2.360)			0.477** (5.711)	0.296** (3.441)	0.0419 (0.350)			-0.100* (-2.504)	0.014 (0.106)		-0.009 (-0.087)
Lag 2	-0.158 (-1.970)			0.395** (5.309)	0.267* (3.162)	-0.223* (-2.005)			-0.069 (-1.738)	0.110 (0.991)		-0.217* (-2.509)
Lag 3				0.128* (2.285)	0.214* (2.724)				-0.051 (-1.665)	-0.307** (-2.950)		0.180** (3.345)
Macros												
EMPUKQ		-0.000* (-1.985)		-0.000 (-0.281)						0.000 (1.307)		
GDP	0.000 (-0.737)			0.000 (0.758)		-0.000 (-1.670)			0.000 (0.085)			
CPI	-0.003 (-2.717)			-0.000 (-0.078)	-0.001 (-0.421)		-0.000 (-0.097)			-0.004 (-1.150)		0.005** (3.078)
IR				-0.003 (-1.722)					0.004* (2.089)			
ECM	-0.193** (-7.383)	-0.335** (-6.527)	-0.425** (-9.812)	-0.827** (-8.469)	-0.362 (-7.333)	-0.347** (-6.759)	-0.556** (-6.752)	-0.263** (-4.653)	-0.414** (-7.895)	-0.390** (-5.545)	-0.266** (-7.498)	-0.916** (-12.696)
R-squared	0.838	0.791	0.814	0.885		0.641	0.742	0.742	0.785	0.717	0.847	0.838

Notes: See Table 3.

Table 5. Conditional ECM Estimates: Old Houses												
Variable	W Mids	E Mids	SW	NW	London	North	Y & H	E Anglia	Scotland	Wales	Outer SE	Outer Met.
Old lag 1	0.164* (2.304)		-0.259** (-4.448)			-0.369** (-5.782)	-0.134 (-1.824)	-0.248** (-3.430)	-0.150 (-1.939)	0.103 (1.063)		-0.334** (-4.306)
Lag 2			-0.233** (-4.884)			-0.291** (-4.236)			-0.006 (-0.104)	0.153 (1.780)		-0.181* (-2.323)
Lag 3						-0.133* (-2.211)			0.111 (2.114)	0.113 (1.434)	-0.038 (-1.339)	
New						0.075 (1.608)	-0.162** (-3.820)		0.090* (1.892)	-0.209** (-5.331)		
Lag 1						0.275** (5.411)	-0.109* (-2.456)					
Lag 2						0.122* (2.153)						
Lag 3						0.185** (3.669)						
Modern				0.309** (4.572)	0.445** (5.933)	0.441** (5.260)	0.177* (2.344)	0.487** (4.936)	0.848** (10.498)	0.501** (6.287)	0.289** (3.876)	0.286** (6.605)
Lag 1	0.463 (4.640)				0.270** (3.510)			0.272** (3.278)	0.284** (2.749)	-0.370** (-2.872)	-0.190* (-2.366)	0.270** (5.136)
Lag 2	-0.258** (-2.589)				0.039 (0.532)			0.189* (2.609)		0.065 (0.612)		0.264** (4.939)
Lag 3					0.356** (6.112)					-0.234* (-2.576)		0.166** (3.691)
Neighbour												
Old	0.275** (2.504)	0.205** (3.179)		0.097 (1.901)	0.473** (4.647)			0.889** (6.777)	-0.027 (-0.582)	0.227 (1.486)	0.499 (7.322)	0.322** (5.408)
Lag 1		0.085 (1.275)		-0.079 (-1.742)	-0.042 (-0.415)			0.134** (2.943)	-0.311* (-2.084)	-0.124 (-1.752)		0.055 (0.730)
Lag 2		-0.216** (-4.201)		-0.129** (-3.138)	-0.187 (-1.918)				-0.104 (-0.638)	-0.087** (-1.446)		0.171 (2.397)
Lag 3									-0.432** (-2.936)	-0.178** (-4.161)		

Table 5. Continued												
New		-0.017 (-0.286)	0.040 (1.087)	0.012 (0.354)	0.043 (1.045)	0.033 (0.339)	0.071 (1.218)					0.059 (1.849)
Lag 1		0.151* (2.487)	0.090* (2.267)				0.387** (5.952)					-0.052 (-1.458)
Lag 2			0.121** (3.143)				0.131* (2.060)					-0.055 (-1.593)
Lag 3			-0.051 (-1.585)									-0.082** (-2.703)
Modern	-0.085 (-0.559)		0.186* (2.529)	0.180* (2.342)	-0.183* (-2.357)		0.345** (3.333)		0.160 (1.074)	0.242** (2.743)		0.253** (3.185)
Lag 1	0.369* (2.606)		0.192** (2.617)				0.098 (0.912)		0.542** (3.195)	0.302** (3.236)		0.061 (0.611)
Lag 2	-0.355** (-3.632)						-0.296** (-3.112)		0.260 (1.486)	0.144 (1.887)		-0.127 (-1.577)
Lag 3	0.393** (4.836)								0.568** (3.334)			-0.134* (-2.439)
Macros												
EMPUKQ			0.000 (1.970)	0.000 (1.509)	0.000** (2.749)				-0.000** (-2.962)	0.000** (2.851)		
GDP	0.006 (3.774)			0.000* (2.254)	0.000 (-0.212)		0.000 (-0.454)	0.000* (2.218)	0.000 (0.531)	0.000 (-0.349)		
CPI	0.000 (1.713)	-0.000 (-0.128)		0.006** (3.336)	0.002 (0.748)	0.005 (1.484)	0.009** (2.890)	0.007* (2.250)	0.009** (3.393)	0.009* (2.353)	0.004** (2.940)	
IR												-0.000 (-0.136)
ECM	-0.785** (-10.131)	-0.577** (-10.956)	-0.486** (-11.513)	-0.859** (-12.428)	-0.545** (-8.393)	-0.484** (-7.874)	-0.536** (-8.478)	-0.699** (-7.526)	-0.428** (-5.188)	-0.797** (-7.500)	-0.658** (-9.691)	-0.364** (-7.532)
R-squared	0.765	0.746		0.827	0.743	0.764	0.801	0.712	0.694	0.746	0.873	0.901

Notes: See Table 3.

-0.149 (Scotland) to -0.345 (East Anglia). This signifies that roughly 14.9% to 34.5% of a quarter's deviation is reversed in the next quarter. Second lag terms are also significant in six of the cointegrated regions, reflecting additional mean-reversion dynamics beyond the first quarter. A significant third lag correction appears in London and Yorkshire and Humberside. These findings reinforce that modern-house markets exhibit strong self-correction behaviour, with adjustment concentrated in the first one or two quarters (H4).

Positive old-house innovations significantly stimulate modern-house growth in Northwest, London, East Anglia and Scotland. Lagged negative coefficients in most of these same regions imply that old-stock shocks temporarily boost modern stock prices before decelerating as markets rebalance. This pattern confirms H3A that, in supply-constrained areas, rising values of existing stock 'push' developers to increase modern completions.

However, in contrast to theory, none of the contemporaneous or lagged new-house terms are shown to be significant in the modern-house ECMs. This indicates that once equilibrium dynamics and controls are accounted for, shocks in new-house growth have no detectable short-run effect on modern-house changes.

Looking at immediate neighbour growth, highly significant and large positive coefficients are shown in every cointegrated region. This demonstrates that local modern-house growth is strongly tied to the immediate quarter's neighbour-average performance (H2). This relationship is reinforced by lag 1 effects being positive in some regions, as this indicates that momentum spillovers persist into the following quarter. However, the lag 1 effects in Northwest and Wales contradict this and instead indicate cyclical overshooting.

Similar to new-house dynamics, the macroeconomic fundamentals play a small but non-negligible role.

5.2.3 Old-House Price Dynamics

Table 5 reveals that lagged changes in local old-house prices exhibit partial persistence and mean reversion. In five regions, the first-lag coefficient is significant and ranges from 0.164 (West Midland), indicating inertia, to -0.369 in Yorkshire and Humberside. This reflects an over-correction rebound and the second lag terms reinforce these adjustment dynamics. The Southwest, North and Outer Metropolitan regions all show negative second lag coefficients, implying that 18% to 29% of the previous quarter's deviation is reversed two quarters on. These results substantiate that old-house markets self-correct after shocks, with adjustment largely concentrated within two quarters (H4).

Moreover, growth in modern housing locally exerts positive significant short-run effects on old-house prices in eight regions, indicating that rising modern stock values 'push' up older stock prices (H3A). These push effects persist at lag 1 in some regions and thus suggests an initial overshoot followed by a moderation as markets rebalance.

Contemporaneous new-house growth shows a positive but statistically weak spillover only in the North and Scotland. However, significant negative impacts are observed in Wales and Yorkshire and Humberside, consistent with buyers substituting toward new stock. Furthermore, lagged new-house effects in the North suggests a more drawn-out 'pull' process where buyer rotations influence old-stock values over several quarters (H3B).

Spatial spillovers remain a dominant force on old-house markets as the contemporaneous neighbour-old coefficient is highly significant and positive in most regions. This confirms that local old-price growth follows neighbour average performance closely. First lag effects are less significant but still present in majority of these same regions, indicating the persistence of regional shocks into subsequent quarters.

Lastly, the macroeconomic fundamentals again play a subsidiary role.

5.2.4 Comparison of Short-Run Dynamics with Hudson et al. (2017)

To determine the impact of controlling macro-financials, we compare our estimated short-run coefficients (Tables 3 to 5) against those reported by Hudson et al. (2017).

Across all three house-types, both studies report highly significant negative first lag coefficients to indicate self-correcting behaviour (H4). However, Hudson et al.'s (2018) estimates exhibit systematically larger magnitudes across new- and old-house-types. In both samples, significant second and third lag terms reinforce the correction in a minority of regions. However, Hudson et al.'s (2017) higher order lags appear more pervasive. Nonetheless, both studies confirm that over half of disequilibrium is absorbed within one quarter, with diminishing persistence thereafter.

Vintage spillovers into neighbouring regions remain pronounced in our study. Modern to new and modern to old effects are in fact larger in our study. However, old to new impacts have become more regionally differentiated and exhibit a stronger negative 'pull' in some regions. New to modern and new to old coefficients remain modest and sporadic across both studies, therefore highlighting their secondary role.

In both studies, spatial propagation remains the most powerful short-run driver as contemporaneous neighbour effects remain highly significant across most regions, although the pattern of strongest feedback as shifted in some regions. The lagged neighbour terms continue to exhibit the same overshoot or adjust cycle yet, this pattern is marginally more pronounced in our study.

Hudson et al. (2017) does not include macro-financial variables in their study. However, these variables in our study enter the short-run with some statistically significant but overall quantitatively minor coefficients. Therefore, the inclusion of these controls does not attenuate the core ripple effects and confirms that the spatial and inter-vintage housing linkages identified in Hudson et al.'s (2017) study persist as the dominant forces shaping short-run UK house-price dynamics.

5.3 Long-Run Dynamics: Conditional ECM Estimates

5.3.1 Long-Run Elasticities for New-House Prices

Table 6 reports that the long-run impact of old-house price growth on new-house growth varies distinctly by region, in line with H3A/B. For example, West Midlands exhibits a strong negative elasticity and indicates that a sustained 1% rise in old-house prices eventually depresses new-house prices by 1.36%. In contrast, the East Midlands, Yorkshire and Humberside and East Anglia yield positive elasticities, reflecting the ‘push’ effects where higher legacy stock values encourage new supply. Modern-house spillovers into new-house markets are significant in Wales and Outer Metropolitan, thus confirming H5.

Moreover, long-run neighbour average old-house growth exerts a significant negative influence in some regions. This suggests that persistent rises in neighbouring legacy stock prices eventually crowd out local new-house activity (H3B). Contemporaneous neighbour new-house growth displays highly significant uniformly positive elasticities. Therefore, a pervasive ripple is present (H2) and a sustained increase in surrounding new-house price growth thus raises the local long-run new-house price level by 0.17% to 1.80%.

The long-run coefficients on the macro-financial variables are generally small but often significant. Employment growth exerts a modest negative long-run elasticity in some regions, whereas CPI innovations enter positively. Real GDP and IR effects are mostly negligible. Thus, the inclusion of these controls marginally adjusts the magnitude of house-type and spatial elasticities but, the long-run ripples remain robust to broader macroeconomic fundamentals.

5.3.2 Long-Run Elasticities for Modern-House Price

Table 7 shows that old-house price growth exerts a uniformly significant positive long-run effect on modern-house prices in ten regions. This robust ‘push’ linkage confirms H3A, that a sustained increase in legacy stock values incentivise modern

Table 6. Long-run Coefficients: New Houses												
Variable	W Mids	E Mids	SW	NW	London	North	Y & H	E Anglia	Scotland	Wales	Outer SE	Outer Met.
Old	-1.357** (-2.744)	0.362* (2.343)	-0.228 (-0.706)	0.809* (2.330)			0.736* (2.498)	0.710* (2.659)	0.454* (2.701)	-0.401** (-2.826)	-0.046 (-0.064)	-0.561* (-2.348)
Modern	0.525 (1.512)	-0.176 (-0.981)	0.544* (2.050)	0.472 (1.409)			-0.322 (-0.992)	0.143 (0.548)	0.114 (0.518)	0.814** (4.841)	0.141 (0.226)	1.184** (4.225)
Neighbour												
Old	0.333 (0.642)	-0.458* (-2.231)	0.454* (2.583)	-0.894** (-3.057)			-0.158 (-0.461)	-0.454 (-1.165)	-0.294* (-2.291)	0.137 (0.694)	-0.580 (-0.815)	0.063 (0.238)
New	0.910** (3.792)	0.379** (4.292)	0.547** (2.810)	0.172* (2.567)			0.459** (3.335)	1.279** (6.875)	0.338** (6.178)	0.506** (4.334)	1.803** (4.581)	0.265* (2.902)
Modern	0.452 (0.9684)	0.716** (2.952)	0.195 (-0.969)	0.329 (1.040)			0.336 (0.845)	-0.506 (-1.350)	0.163 (1.375)	-0.139 (-0.527)	-0.248 (-0.385)	0.092 (0.357)
Macros												
EMPUKQ	0.000** (3.042)	-0.000** (-6.048)	-0.000* (-2.496)	-0.000** (-4.755)			-0.000 (-0.446)	0.000 (1.674)	-0.000* (-2.413)	-0.000 (-1.553)	-6.29E-05 (-1.602)	7.13E-06 (0.644)
GDP	-0.000 (-1.426)	0.000** (3.257)	0.000 (0.111)				-0.000 (-0.494)	-0.000 (-0.312)	0.000 (1.055)	-0.000 (-0.470)	3.34E-06 (1.862)	-1.39E-06* (-2.715)
CPI	-0.000 (-0.160)	0.005** (8.598)	0.000 (-0.346)	0.003** (3.832)			0.000 (0.3216)	-0.003** (-3.112)	0.0005** (6.605)	0.000** (4.752)	-0.007* (-2.886)	0.002* (2.530)
IR	0.000 (0.032)	0.007* (1.794)	0.001 (0.129)	-0.000 (-0.373)			-0.002 (-0.265)	-0.008 (-1.171)	0.007* (1.642)	0.009 (1.631)	-0.010 (-0.803)	0.001 (0.275)
Constant	-1.109* (-2.201)	1.404** (7.761)	0.415 (1.311)	1.794** (5.869)			0.224 (0.482)	-0.809 (-1.875)	1.095** (3.590)	0.414 (1.823)	1.022 (1.237)	-0.120 (-0.538)

Notes: See Table 3.

Table 7. Long-run Coefficients: Modern Houses												
Variable	W Mids	E Mids	SW	NW	London	North	Y & H	E Anglia	Scotland	Wales	Outer SE	Outer Met.
New												
Old	1.161** (6.829)	0.610** (5.275)	0.739** (10.767)	0.757** (7.214)	0.679** (3.998)	0.643** (3.731)	0.343** (2.974)		0.617** (7.893)		1.131** (7.152)	0.752** (10.572)
Neighbour												
Modern	-0.420 (-0.760)	0.904* (3.275)	0.009 (0.076)	0.887** (5.955)	0.835* (2.744)	0.415 (0.786)	0.920** (6.088)		0.157 (1.410)		0.681* (2.235)	0.372** (3.372)
New	0.099 (0.498)	-0.075 (-0.707)	0.479** (7.654)	0.049* (2.232)	0.220 (1.533)	0.002 (0.015)	-0.203** (-3.327)		-0.050 (-1.0380)		-0.063 (-0.431)	0.110* (2.601)
Old	0.165 (0.280)	-0.428 (-1.687)	-0.217 (-1.597)	-0.632** (-5.358)	-0.732* (-2.336)	-0.165 (-0.347)	0.009 (0.063)		0.250* (2.553)		-0.916** (-2.985)	-0.279* (-2.135)
Macros												
EMPUKQ	-0.000 (-0.239)	0.000 (1.556)	-0.000 (-0.142)	0.000 (1.193)	0.000 (1.960)	-0.000 (-0.145)	0.000 (1.532)		-0.000 (-0.383)		-0.000** (-2.946)	-0.000 (-1.312)
GDP	0.000 (0.327)	-0.000 (-1.624)	0.000 (1.536)	-0.000* (-3.069)	0.000 (-0.396)	0.000 (0.765)	-0.000** (-3.446)		-0.000 (-1.608)		0.000** (3.345)	0.000 (0.882)
CPI	0.000 (0.123)	-0.001 (-1.203)	-0.003** (-5.450)	0.001 (2.273)	-0.001 (-0.903)	-0.000 (-0.075)	0.002** (2.948)		-0.000 (-0.035)		0.001 (0.728)	0.000 (0.803)
IR	0.015 (1.890)	-0.004 (-0.748)	0.002 (0.543)	-0.004 (-1.356)	-0.006 (-0.926)	0.004 (0.547)	0.005 (1.450)		-0.005 (-1.325)		-0.001 (-0.187)	-0.001 (-0.308)
Constant	-0.100 (-0.190)	-0.124 (-0.612)	0.039 (0.218)	-0.222 (-1.229)	-0.599 (-1.829)	0.321 (0.747)	-0.459* (-2.032)		0.522* (2.523)		1.472** (3.358)	0.291** (3.031)

Notes: See Table 3.

Table 8. Long-run Coefficients: Old Houses												
Variable	W Mids	E Mids	SW	NW	London	North	Y & H	E Anglia	Scotland	Wales	Outer SE	Outer Met.
New	-0.032 (-0.635)	0.240* (2.433)	0.132 (1.378)	0.030 (0.672)	0.047 (1.088)	-0.021 (-0.195)	0.155 (1.134)	0.073 (1.021)		-0.156 (-1.762)	0.061 (1.385)	-0.122 (-1.334)
Modern	0.667** (13.413)	0.782** (7.684)	1.114** (9.675)	0.706** (7.619)	0.656** (4.426)	0.614** (4.175)	-0.011 (-0.045)	0.655** (5.815)		1.202** (16.156)	0.864** (13.491)	0.475 (1.930)
Neighbour												
Old	0.920** (5.500)	0.565** (3.441)	0.127 (1.003)	0.296** (4.023)	0.547* (2.551)	0.751** (2.340)	0.829** (4.910)	0.729** (3.489)		0.422 (1.795)	0.806** (5.820)	0.754** (3.493)
New	0.089 (1.114)	-0.264** (-3.024)	-0.369** (-3.360)	-0.037 (-1.756)	0.156 (1.295)	-0.566* (-2.048)	-0.044 (-0.369)	-0.065 (-0.501)		-0.110 (-1.163)	0.004 (0.062)	0.183 (1.605)
Modern	-0.620** (-3.467)	-0.211 (-1.051)	-0.063 (-0.488)	0.050 (0.426)	-0.468 (-1.789)	0.300 (0.766)	0.176 (0.608)	-0.526* (-2.281)		-0.421 (-1.414)	-0.648** (-4.045)	-0.215 (-1.050)
Macros												
EMPUKQ	0.000** (5.516)	0.000 (0.453)	-0.000 (-1.812)	0.000** (3.104)	0.000 (0.112)	-0.000** (-3.046)	0.000** (3.876)	-0.000** (-4.367)		-0.000 (-0.778)	0.000* (2.523)	0.000 (0.723)
GDP	-0.000** (-6.397)	0.000 (-1.110)	0.000 (1.712)	0.000 (-1.969)	0.000 (0.621)	0.000 (0.580)	-0.000** (-3.383)	0.000** (5.779)		0.000 (1.948)	-0.000** (-3.608)	-0.000** (-2.910)
CPI	-0.000 (-0.936)	-0.002* (-2.231)	0.002** (2.464)	-0.001* (-3.036)	0.003** (4.683)	-0.000 (-0.056)	-0.001 (-1.282)	0.001 (1.513)		0.001 (1.482)	-0.001* (-2.577)	-0.000 (-0.260)
IR	-0.003 (-1.164)	-0.002 (-0.570)	-0.007 (-1.966)	-0.002 (-1.306)	0.006 (1.462)	-0.017* (-2.501)	-0.006 (-1.269)	-0.006 (-1.306)		0.005 (1.117)	-0.005* (-2.050)	-0.012* (-2.412)
Constant	-0.636** (-3.893)	-0.356 (-1.628)	0.471* (1.993)	-0.387** (-3.449)	-0.087 (-0.360)	1.281** (2.779)	-1.020** (-3.357)	1.175** (5.245)		0.145 (0.625)	-0.430** (-3.531)	0.068 (0.409)

Notes: See Table 3.

completions over the long-run. In contrast, the direct long-run spillover from new-house growth into modern prices is generally weak and insignificant. This suggests that new to modern transmission is secondary once equilibrium dynamics have played out.

Furthermore, neighbour average modern-house price growth shows highly positive elasticities in some regions. These large coefficients confirm the endurance of the spatial ripple of contemporaneous peer market performance (H2). Despite this, West Midlands and Southwest do not display significant linkages and this indicates regional heterogeneity in long-run spatial integration.

Similar to new-house prices, macro fundamentals play a secondary role in shaping long-run modern-house price differentials once house-type and spatial dynamics are accounted for.

5.3.3 Long-Run Elasticities for Old-House Price

In Table 8, nine regions exhibit significant large positive long-run elasticities on old-house prices. This robust linkage confirms that sustained new-build activity elevates legacy stock values over the long-run (H3A). In contrast, the direct effect of new-house growth on old-house prices is generally weak and insignificant as only few regions showing modest positive elasticities. This suggests that new growth plays a secondary role in shaping the long-run trajectory of older stock prices, once equilibrium forces have operated.

Additionally, spatial spillovers from neighbouring old-house markets are uniformly significantly positive in nine regions. This highlights the persistence of a multi-dimensional ripple effect (H1) as these large coefficients indicate that a 1% sustained increase in adjacent regions' old stock growth increases local old price by 0.30% to 0.92% in the long-run.

Unlike the other house types, employment growth exhibits significant positive elasticities in four regions. This implies that stronger labour market conditions support

old-houses values in the long-run. Moreover, real GDP shows a significant negative effect in some regions while CPI enters with mixed signs. IR elasticities are generally small and only marginally significant.

5.3.4 Comparison of Long-Run Elasticities with Hudson et al. (2017)

Across each house-type, our long-run estimates broadly match Hudson et al.'s (2017) findings. For example, for new houses, both studies observe rapid self-correction. However, our recorded adjustment speeds are slightly more moderate. Although our study provides large neighbour-average effects, Hudson et al. (2017) spatial spillovers prove even stronger. This suggests that contemporary ripple mechanisms have weakened once macro-financials have been controlled. Furthermore, our cross-vintage impacts from modern into new houses are also smaller and suggest a possible decreased 'push' impact from more recently completed homes.

Moreover, for modern houses, the influence of legacy stock on new deliveries remains strong in our study. However, our older stock elasticities tend to be smaller than that of Hudson et al. (2017) and this indicates that our study has less pronounced supply substitution dynamics. In both studies, neighbour-average modern growth continues to dominate local momentum but, again, is lower in our work. Furthermore, the direct effect of new stock expansions on modern prices have become weaker in our study, and occasionally non-significant once macro-financials are controlled.

Lastly, for old house, both studies confirm that modern completions significantly increase legacy value in the long-run. Overall, introducing macroeconomic controls into the model fails to achieve significant dampening to these fundamental ripple patterns.

6. Conclusion

By integrating macro-financial controls, we demonstrate that core ripple effects remain robust to the inclusion of broad aggregate shocks. Despite employment, GDP, CPI and IR innovations each exhibiting occasional significant regionally heterogeneous short-run effects, their overall contribution to explaining quarterly price changes is modest relative to network dynamics. This finding confirms that genuine regional contagion and local supply-demand interactions cannot be simply attributed to common macroeconomic disturbances.

Our disaggregated vintage analysis clarifies how different segments of the housing stock interact in both the short-run and long-run. Modern house innovation persistently ‘pushes’ new-build growth as this reflects developer’s responsiveness to rising contemporary-spec completions. In contrast, older stock effects oscillate between positive supply responses in looser markets and ‘pull’-type substitution in overheated contexts. These nuanced vintage-specific patterns deepen our understanding of which segments drive aggregate momentum and where policy interventions may yield the greatest benefits, such as targeted planning.

By re-estimating the regional ARDL equation with macro-financial controls, we uncover mild attenuation in the magnitude of neighbour-average coefficients. This attenuation quantifies the extent to which previous ripple studies may have marginally overstated spatial spillover by omitting macroeconomic fundamentals. However, the persistence of significant network coefficients even after controlling for these fundamentals demonstrates that regional housing policies, connectivity and migration dynamics remain central to price propagation across the UK.

This study can be utilised in policy making as UK macroprudential and monetary policymakers should recognise that local effects drive the transfer of shocks from one region to another, whereas broad cyclical factors shape the general housing environment. Thus, regional and vintage-targeted measures can complement broad national policy to more tackle overheating or support housing supply in lagging regions.

Finally, this study's approach highlights sustainable avenues for future research. Incorporating mortgage credit spreads, for example, could further disentangle the interplay between finance and local spatial dynamics. Furthermore, applying this augmented framework to cross-country comparisons may shed light on how housing system structure and macro-prudential regimes condition the transmission of regional price shocks. Overall, by combining vintage-specific network analysis with macro-financial variables, this dissertation advances both the empirical toolkit and the policy dialogue on regional housing market dynamics in the UK and globally.

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Notes:

Data available at: <http://www.nationwide.co.uk/about/house-price-index/download-data#xtab:regional-quarterly-series-all-properties-data-available-from-1973-onwards>.